

JURISPRUDENCE

THE TRIAL PROCEDURE ON THE BASIS OF SAMPLING ADMINISTRATION IN THE CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS. COMPREHENSIVE RIGHT ASPECTS

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Abstract

We believe that in order to maximally exclude the possibility of "taking over" the practice of a country and, moreover, of a different legal system, thus avoiding a great danger of also taking over certain stereotypes or misperceiving these practices, the working group, u researched numerous foreign normative acts regarding the simplified procedure in question, to which we will refer in the following lines. In the same way, we will relate the context in which this institution appeared and exists, as well as the way in which it was regulated and adapted by each country for its needs.

Keywords: amendment, legislation, criminal procedure, judicial investigation.

In accordance with the Law on the amendment and completion of the Code of Criminal Procedure no. 66 of 04/05/2012, entered into force on 10/27/2012, the domestic criminal procedure code was supplemented with art. 364/1, by which a new way of simplified procedures for adjudicating criminal cases was established. A new institution that provides for the trial of the case based on the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase. In the following, we will examine the emergence and regulation of this institution and its applicability in Romania.

Therefore, according to Romanian legislation, namely according to law no. 202/2010 regarding some measures to accelerate the resolution of trials, important changes were also made in the Romanian criminal process.

Therefore, in chapter II (Judgment in first instance), in section I (Proceeding of cases) of the Romanian Criminal Procedure Code, according to art. 320 was introduced art. 320/1, which establishes the manner of carrying out the judgment in case of admission of guilt.

This text, which establishes, in fact, a true special court procedure, appears as a new element in 2010 in the Romanian criminal procedure, being an institution that precedes the plea agreement procedure regulated by art. 478-488 of the new Criminal Procedure Code of Romania.

Comparing the way of admitting guilt in the present simplified procedure, we note that art. 320/1 para. (1) of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure establishes "Until the start of the judicial investigation, the defendant can declare in person or through an authentic document that he recognizes the commission of the facts recorded in the court's report and requests that the judgment be made on the basis of the evidence administered in the phase of prosecution".

Thus, from the content of this text it follows that the admission of guilt can be made either through the statement taken from the defendant by the court, or through an authentic document, in which case the trial can take place without the presence of the defendant.

From the corroborated reading of the provisions of para. (1) cited above and para. (3) "at the time of trial,

the court asks the defendant if he requests that the trial take place on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase, which he knows and acquires, proceeds to his hearing and then gives the floor to the prosecutor and the other parties ", it appears that the trial could take place even without the presence of the defendant only if in the authentic document submitted to the file he states that he requests that the trial take place on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase, "which he knows and appropriates", as provided by art. 320/1 para. (3) of the Criminal Procedure Code.

However, comparing the legislative text enunciated with the legal text established in the domestic legal framework, according to art. 364/1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, we note that "until the start of the judicial investigation, the defendant can declare, personally through an authentic document, that he recognizes the commission of the facts indicated in the indictment and requests that the judgment be made on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase".

Taking into account the content of the statement, it appears that it must be express and unequivocal, and the authentic document of the defendant will include both the recognition of the fact/facts described in the indictment, as well as the request that the judgment be made on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase.

The unequivocal character of the recognition requires that the written document contains a sufficiently clear manifestation of will, by referring to the facts retained in the indictment, the request that the judgment be made on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation, specifying the knowledge and appropriation of this evidence, as well as the waiver when administering other tests.

These conditions must be met cumulatively, bearing in mind that the defendant's statement is not a formal act, but also a substantive one.

In this sense, we note that according to the national legislation, the cumulation of both "in person" and "by authentic document" conditions is mandatory, conditions which according to the Romanian legislation can

also be "in person" or "by authentic document" alternatives.

Regarding the object and limits of the recognition of guilt, I note that the object of the recognition, from the marginal name of the text of art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure, which reads as follows "Judgment in case of admission of guilt", it appears that it refers to "guilt", but from the reading of para. (1) of this text shows that the recognition refers to "committing the facts recorded in the court notification".

Comparing with the marginal name of the text of art. 364/1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova, which is called "Judgment based on the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase", we note that from the name of the article provided by the national legislation, the idea of recognizing the commission of the facts, specifically those retained in the drawn up indictment, is clearer by the prosecutor during the criminal investigation phase.

Analyzing the purpose of the procedure regulated by art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure, as well as the purpose of the procedure provided for in art. 364/1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova, it still remains a unique and common one, namely, the urgency of the court procedure, which is done only on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase.

As for the offenses in which the provisions of art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure in comparison with art. 364/1 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Moldova, art. 320/1 para. (7) provides that this procedure is applicable to the trial of all crimes punishable by imprisonment or a fine, the final sentence of this paragraph establishing "the provisions of para. (1)-(6) do not apply if the criminal action concerns a crime punishable by life imprisonment", while art. 364/1, para. (8) provides that this procedure is applicable to the trial of all crimes punishable by imprisonment or a fine, including crimes for which life imprisonment is established, this fact being expressly established by the legislation in force, namely "If the punishment provided by law is life imprisonment, the prison sentence of 30 years is applied".

However, another similarity between art. 320/1 para. (1) from the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure and art. 364/1, para. (1) of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova would be the imposition of a time limit, namely "until the start of the judicial investigation".

Regarding the court procedure in the case of the application of the provisions of art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure, the trial will take place, as provided in para. (2) of the article, i.e. only on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase, the normative text imposing two cumulative conditions: the defendant declares that he fully recognizes the facts recorded in the court's referral act and does not request the administration of other evidence, except circumstantial documents.

To be admitted as evidence under art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure, the circumstantial documents must be administered at the court

term in which the full recognition of the facts recorded in the referral document takes place. If their administration would not be possible at this time, causing the case to be postponed in this sense, the defendant will not be able to use the special procedure regulated by art. 320/1 of the Romanian Criminal Procedure Code.

Thus, we note that from a procedural point of view, both the legal provisions of Romania and those of the Republic of Moldova are guided by the same steps and the same principles. These can be directly observed even from the comparison of legal texts which are very similar to each other in this respect.

By way of consequences, we mention that if the court finds that all the conditions imposed by art. 320/1-364/1 of the Codes of Criminal Procedure, resulting from the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase, namely that the facts of the defendant or defendants are established, being sufficient data regarding his or her person to allow the establishment of a punishment, then the court will accept the defendant's request and will order the trial based on art. 364/1-320/1 of the Criminal Procedure Codes.

If the court rejects the defendant's request that the trial take place on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase, according to the provisions of art. 320/1 of the Romanian Criminal Procedure Code, the trial will continue according to common law procedure.

Regarding the civil action exercised through the criminal process, from the contrary interpretation of the provisions of art. 320/1 para. (5) of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure, it follows that this can be resolved together with the criminal action only when it is not required to take evidence before the court, or when the defendant fully recognizes the claims of the civil party, under the conditions of art. 161 para. (2) of the Romanian Criminal Procedure Code, either when, in the criminal investigation phase, sufficient evidence has been administered regarding the civil action. A similar approach to the given subject can be deduced from the analysis of the Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Republic of Moldova regarding the application of the provisions of art. 364/1 Code of criminal procedure by the courts. However, in the context in which the provisions of art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure do not contain special provisions, in the matter of appeals the provisions of common law in the field are applied, the sentence handed down can be challenged, as the case may be, by appeal or appeal, there being no legal rules to regulate these appeals attack in the matter of the guilty plea procedure. Therefore, in appeals, nothing stops the defendant from requesting the administration of any admissible means of evidence, which means that the simplified court procedure can be annihilated in the subsequent stages of judicial control, the purpose pursued by the legislator by adopting it being thus compromise.

On another note, I mention that the provisions of art. 320/1 para. (7) of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure also regulates the effects of the application of the special procedure of admission of guilt, providing that the court will sentence the defendant, who benefits from the reduction by one third of the punishment

limits provided by law in the case of prison sentences and from the reduction by one fourth of the penalty limits provided by law, in the case of a fine.

The legislator limited *expressis verbis* through this text of the law the solution that the judge can pronounce, which is always that of conviction, there being no possibility of pronouncing acquittal or ending the criminal process, the role of the magistrate judge becoming one limited only to the individualization of criminal punishments, he no longer having a full jurisdictional function.

Emerging from these, the similarity with the national legislation can be observed in terms of the effect of the application of the procedure in question. Considering the fact that the provisions of art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure does not regulate aspects other than those provided for in para. 7, in the case of a contest between the causes of aggravation or, respectively, mitigation of the punishment, the provisions of art. 80 Criminal Procedure Code. The application of the special court procedure regulated by art. 320/1 of the Romanian Criminal Procedure Code does not exclude, therefore, the simultaneous application of other causes of aggravation or mitigation of the punishment, the punishment limits being those reduced according to the provisions of para. (7) of the same article.

However, according to Romanian legislation, the judge when applying the simplified procedure provided for in art. 320/1 of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure is deprived of the possibility of an acquittal in the simplified procedure, on the grounds that the deed does not present the level of social danger of a crime, which in our opinion compromises the purpose of the law, and creates a more procedural situation favorable to the person who commits an act that presents the degree of social danger of a crime. It should be noted that according to national legislation, during the examination of the case in the simplified procedure provided for in art. 364/1, both the sentence of conviction and acquittal or termination of the criminal process can be adopted, subject to appeals under general conditions.

At the same time, in practice there may also be situations where the defendant resorts to the procedure regulated by art. 320/1 of the Romanian Criminal Procedure Code, requesting that the judgment be made only on the basis of the evidence administered during the criminal investigation phase, and that the court find that the criminal investigation documents are struck by absolute nullity. We note that, prior to the start of this procedure, which can take place until "the beginning of the judicial investigation", the court is obliged to verify the regularity of the notification act. The indictment must be limited to the facts and persons for whom the criminal investigation was carried out, which implies a legally initiated criminal investigation.

Starting from this premise, the verification of the way in which the legal provisions relating to the referral to the court were respected should not be limited only to the content of the indictment, but should look at all the procedural and procedural documents that are its basis and that are reflected in its content. As such, the

preliminary control of regularity of the act of notification to the court and verification of the legal provisions regarding the notification to the court also includes the examination of the manner of compliance with the legal provisions regarding the initiation of the criminal prosecution, the carrying out of the criminal prosecution against the accused and the initiation of the action criminal.

In this context, if it is found that there is any violation of the imperative rules regarding jurisdiction by matter or by the quality of the person, the notification of the court, the presence of the accused or the defendant and his assistance by the defense attorney, sanctioned with absolute nullity, the court will have to order the return of the case to the prosecutor for the reopening of the criminal investigation.

The application of this text is mandatory for the court, although it is positioned in the topography of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure according to art. 320/1, gaining procedural relevance through the provisions of art. 300 para. (1) in conjunction with those of art. 263 para. (1) of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure, in the context in which the sanction provided by law in the case of these violations is absolute nullity, which according to art. 197 para. (2) of the Romanian Code of Criminal Procedure, cannot be removed in any way, being able to be invoked in any state of the process and being taken into account *ex officio*.

Therefore, the recognition of the defendant cannot confirm the null acts, even more so as it can only refer to the commission of the facts, so that, in view of the principle of the legality of the criminal process, the court must stop the continuation of the criminal process, even in this variant of summary judgment of the cause, a fact that is also found in the provisions of our national legislation.

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